

Transition metal complexes of heterocyclic ligands. Part-II. Complex compounds of ions with d^6 , d^7 , d^8 and d^{10} electronic configuration with 3-*N*-dibenzofurylthiourea

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The title complexes are found to be of the types $[MLCl_2]$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}$ and Pt^{II} , $[FeL_2Cl_2]$ and $[(CuCl)_2L_2]$, and $L = 3-N$ -dibenzofurylthiourea. The thioamide acts as bidentate ligand using both sulfur and nitrogen atoms as donors. The bacteriostatic activity of the thioamide and the complexes has been determined against selected bacteria.

Sulfur- and nitrogen-containing compounds possess biological activities¹. In many cases, coordination of such compounds to transition metal ions enhances their activity². Here we report six complexes of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pd^{II} , Pt^{II} and Cu^{II} with the thioamide 3-*N*-dibenzofurylthiourea (NDBFT)³.

common organic solvents is medium. The elemental analysis data show that they are of the types $[MLCl_2]$, where $M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}$, $[FeL_2Cl_2]$ and $[(CuCl)_2L_2]$, $L = NDBFT$. Low conductance values ($1.45-3.00 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) in $10^{-3} M$ DMF solutions at room temperature show their non-electrolytic nature.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are microcrystalline coloured powder, whose melting points are higher than the pure thioamide. They are stable at room temperature and their solubility in

IR spectra of the complexes and the thioamide were analysed^{4,5} and the results are presented in Table 1. These studies show that the thioamide acts as bidentate ligand using both sulfur and nitrogen atoms as donors.

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of the ligand and complex

Compd.	νNH_2	δNH_2	νCN coupling C-C	νCN coupling NH ₂	νCS	δNH_2	νNCS	$\nu C=S$
NDBFT (L)	3350 3263	1621	1450	1357	1220	970	850 765 741	670
$[FeL_2Cl_2]$	3348 3266	1620	1456	1355	1220	965	765 742 730	660
$[CoLCl_2]$	3150 3050	1619	1460	1354	1217	960	750 740 725	650
$[NiLCl_2]$	3348 3250	1620	1457	1365	1218	957	763 740 728	655
$[PdLCl_2]$	3357 3172	1619	1460	1357	1220	953	770 750 730	650
$[PtLCl_2]$	3358 3270	1620	1460	1357	1222	958	745	660
$[(CuCl)_2L_2]$	3150 3175	1620	1440	1360	1224	965	755	640

The magnetic moment value of the Fe^{II} complex (4.90 B.M.) indicates that the complex is spin-free and has octahedral geometry. The electronic spectrum shows a broad absorption band at 16600 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_g transition⁶. The magnetic moment value of the Co^{II} complex is 2.16 B.M. Its electronic spectrum displays two bands at 16400 and 21200 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ²A_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²A_{1g} → ²E_g transitions, respectively, in a square-planar configuration around Co^{II}. The Ni^{II} complex is diamagnetic. Its electronic spectrum exhibits four bands at 22200, 30200, 32400 and 37600 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} (ν₁), ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} (ν₂), ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_u (ν₃) and π → π* (L) transitions, respectively. The first two bands are of low intensity and are purely d-d transition, while ν₃ is enveloped by a strong charge transfer transition. These results suggest a square-planar configuration for the Ni^{II} complex⁷. The Pd^{II} complex is diamagnetic. The electronic spectral bands at 16600, 21300 and 30300 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}(ν₁), ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g}(ν₂) and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_{1g}(ν₃) transitions, respectively, in a square-planar configuration around Pd^{II}. The Pt^{II} complex is diamagnetic. The electronic spectrum displays three bands at 21900, 26000 and 30200 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} (ν₁), ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} (ν₂) and ¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g (ν₃) transitions, respectively, in an idealised square-planar symmetry⁷. The Cu^I complex reveals no absorption band in the visible domain and the absorption bands which appear in the UV domain are considered to be characteristic of the ligand. The studies on the Cu^I complex with NDBFT were completed by molecular mass measurements (Rast method). The results suggest that the Cu^I complex possesses structure of a

diamagnetic dimer (molecular weight : calcd. 682.14 and found 680.79).

The structures proposed for the complexes are presented in Chart 1.

Antibacterial activity of ligand and its complexes were studied against *S aureus* and *E coli* by using the diffusion method using streptomycin as control⁸. The ligand did not exhibit remarkable activity (zone of inhibition <6 mm) while the complexes showed moderate activities (9–17 mm). The antibacterial activity was found to increase in the order . [PtLCl₂] > [PdLCl₂] > [NiLCl₂] > [CoLCl₂] > [FeL₂Cl₂] > [(CuCl)₂L₂].

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer FT-1600 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on an Unicam UV2-300 spectrophotometer. The molar conductivity was determined using OK-102 (Hungary) conductivity meter. The magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature.

General procedure : A hot ethanolic solution of thioamide (NDBFT) was added dropwise with continuous stirring to an ethanolic solution of the respective metal dichloride in a 2 : 1 molar ratio. The solution was refluxed for 2 h. The resulting metal complex was washed with ethanol and diethyl ether and then dried under reduced pressure.

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Chart 1